

Application of the LDA Model for Topic Identification: A Case Study on Dengue Diagnosis

Aplicación del Modelo de LDA para la Identificación Temas: Un Caso Aplicado sobre Diagnóstico de Dengue

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Abstract

[Objective]: This research aimed to identify and analyze topics in the scientific literature related to Dengue, with a focus on diagnosis, signs, and symptoms using the Dirichlet Latent Dirichlet Assignment (LDA) Model. **[Methodology]:** Articles were collected from various databases, including VHL, Web of Science, Ovid, Scopus, PubMed, Health & Medical, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar, covering the period from 2000 to 2024. The search equation was designed using key terms such as Dengue, Signs, Symptoms, and Diagnosis, along with MeSH terms to ensure the inclusion of relevant articles. The LDA model was then implemented to analyze the collected articles. **[Results]:** The implementation of the LDA model identified four main themes: 1) Dengue diagnosis and clinical presentation, 2) Research and control interventions, 3) Severe Dengue and its clinical manifestations, and 4) Virus detection, including Dengue, Zika, and Chikungunya. This thematic analysis facilitated the organization and understanding of the literature, providing an overview of the predominant themes in Dengue research. **[Conclusions]:** The study's approach not only enhanced the organization and understanding of the articles found but also provided insights into the predominant themes in Dengue literature, which may guide future research and improve diagnostic and treatment strategies.

Keywords: Text mining; Statistical learning; Text processing; Text recognition; LDA Model; Dengue.

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Resumen

[Objetivo]: Esta investigación tuvo como objetivo identificar y analizar temas de la literatura científica relacionados con el Dengue, con énfasis en el diagnóstico, signos y síntomas utilizando el Modelo de Asignación Latente Dirichlet (LDA). **[Metodología]:** Se recopilaron artículos de diversas bases de datos, incluyendo BVS, Web of Science, Ovid, Scopus, PubMed, Health & Medical, ScienceDirect y Google Scholar, cubriendo el período de 2000 a 2024. La ecuación de búsqueda se diseñó utilizando términos clave como Dengue, Signos, Síntomas y Diagnóstico, junto con términos MeSH para asegurar la inclusión de artículos relevantes. A continuación, se implementó el modelo LDA para analizar los artículos recopilados. **[Resultados]:** La implementación del modelo LDA identificó cuatro temas principales: 1) Diagnóstico y presentación clínica del dengue, 2) Intervenciones de investigación y control, 3) Dengue grave y sus manifestaciones clínicas, y 4) Detección de virus, incluyendo Dengue, Zika y Chikungunya. Este análisis temático facilitó la organización y comprensión de la literatura, proporcionando una visión general de los temas predominantes en la investigación del Dengue. **[Conclusiones]:** El enfoque del estudio no sólo mejoró la organización y comprensión de los artículos encontrados, sino que también proporcionó una visión de los temas predominantes en la literatura sobre el Dengue, lo que puede orientar futuras investigaciones y mejorar las estrategias de diagnóstico y tratamiento.

Keywords: Minería de textos; Aprendizaje estadístico; Procesamiento de textos; Reconocimiento de textos; Modelo LDA; Dengue.

Introduction

According to Luquea et al. (2021), technological advances and advanced search engines make it easier to quickly obtain information on a specific topic. However, access to scientific content in online databases, although diverse, presents difficulties in synthesizing trends in scientific research in a particular area (Gulo and Rúbio, 2015; Trueba-Gómez and Estrada-Lorenzo, 2010). According to Asmussen and Møller (2019), exploratory manual reviews are characterized as a laborious process that requires considerable time and is limited by the processing capacity available, leading to a reduced analysis of articles. While there are several ways to conduct an exploratory review, most methods require a considerable initial investment of time and pre-existing knowledge (Asmussen and Møller, 2019).

For this reason, the literature proposes some techniques, such as those coming from the field of text mining, which allow exploring in a more efficient and structured way the vast amount of available articles. One of these techniques is the Latent Dirichlet Allocation Model (LDA), which represents an advanced information retrieval tool. This model automatically finds general themes in a set of text documents and attempts to identify implicit themes, thus facilitating the automatic organization, understanding, searching and summarizing of numerous documents.

In Asmussen and Møller (2019), the application of the LDA model is suggested as a transparent, reliable, fast, and reproducible process for reviewing large numbers of documents, an essential task in the construction of state-of-the-art for multiple research papers. This article presents the LDA model as a valuable tool that provides an overview of the topic during the exploratory and literature review phase, minimizing the effort before

tackling time-consuming manual reviews. This approach is particularly beneficial for novice researchers or those with limited knowledge in a specific research field.

The LDA model has previously been used to identify concepts and topics as mentioned in the review presented by Asmussen and Møller (2019), where it indicates that most cases have been employed to analyze web content (Ghosh and Guha, 2013; Guo et al., 2016; Elgesem et al., 2016, 2019; Parra et al., 2016), newspaper articles (Koltsova and Koltcov, 2013; DiMaggio et al., 2013; Van Atteveldt et al., 2014; Evans, 2014; Jacobi et al., 2018), books (Jockers and Mimno, 2013), speeches (Quinn et al., 2010) and, in one case, videos (Baum, 2012). The use of the LDA model in the field of medical research is evidenced in several studies. For example, Sahria and Fudholi (2020) employed it to analyze themes in Indonesian health research, while applied it in analyzing news headlines during eight months of the COVID-19 pandemic; in Luquea et al. (2021) they used the approach to examine patterns in Covid-19 scientific research from abstracts published in PubMed during the first half of 2020. Another example is the study by Rojas (2022) on cervical cancer in social networks, where the LDA model was used to identify issues such as the effectiveness of HPV vaccines, the relationship with other diseases and medical programs. Finally, Guzman-Ponce et al. (2023) propose its use to investigate COVID-19 survival factors in Mexico, using data from the Ministry of Health.

The objective of the article is to employ the LDA model to effectively identify and analyze the topics present in the literature related to Dengue diagnosis, due to the volume of articles that can be presented. This approach will allow not only a segmentation of the available information, but also a better orientation to identify and address knowledge gaps in the field of Dengue research. By clearly understanding the predominant themes in this research, synthesis of information will be facilitated and areas that have been underexplored may be identified, suggesting opportunities for future research.

Theoretical Framework

Model LDA

The Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) model is an unsupervised learning model, meaning there is no prior information about the possible topics or themes, or at least they are not predefined. The LDA model is based on a latent variable model derived from the interaction between the observed data and hidden random variables. In this context, the observed data correspond to each text, while the latent variables represent the topics associated with each document (Silvestre, 2018).

Each document, or bag of words, is considered a mixture of several topics assigned by the same algorithm; in this part, it is assumed that the distribution of each topic comes from a Dirichlet probability distribution. This means that the algorithm allows each bag of words (Document) to belong simultaneously to different topics, with a different weight for each topic; that is, each bag of words is more likely to belong to a particular topic than to another (Diaz Rubiano, 2022).

According to Diaz Rubiano (2022), the LDA model has its probabilistic basis in Bayesian statistics; this model makes better use of the available data without the need to collect large amounts of information, thanks to its Bayesian foundation (Blei et al., 2003). The LDA model is based on some basic assumptions. First, it assumes that documents dealing with similar topics use similar words in their content and that topics are distributions of a fixed vocabulary, K topics. These basic assumptions underlie the ability of the LDA model to discover hidden patterns in document sets and to help identify underlying topic structures.

It is important to define the following terms before proceeding (Blei et al., 2003):

- **Corpus:** They represent the set of texts or documents in which we are interested in discovering topics. In our case, it is the set of summaries of articles. It is denoted by: $D = \{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_N\}$, each d_j represents the j -th document.
- **Topics:** These are latent topics or underlying categories that can describe the content of the documents. The LDA model assumes that each document is a mixture of several topics. It is denoted by: $Z = \{z_1, z_2, \dots, z_k\}$, where k represents the number of topics.
- **Words:** They are the most minor units in documents. The LDA model the generation of words in a document from its topics. It is denoted by w_i , where the subscript i indicates the i -th word of the finite collection of words called vocabulary $w = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_N\}$.
- **Term-Document Matrix:** It represents the relationship between terms (words) and documents. Each row of the matrix corresponds to a term, each column to a document, and each cell contains the frequency or weight of the term in the corresponding document. This matrix is fundamental to analyzing and discovering the structure of topics.

Considering a D corpus including a total of M documents, where each j document with $j = 1, 2, \dots, M$ consists of N_j words, the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) model addresses the modeling of this D corpus. Figure 1 shows how the LDA model works.

Figure 1. How does an LDA model work? Extracted from Arteaga and Mendoza, (2023)

Methodology

Article procurement

Documents will be searched in BVS, Web of Science, Ovid, Scopus, PubMed, Health & Medical, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar databases. The search strategy will be based on the equation used by the PubMed database, which offers a vast collection of peer-reviewed medical articles and advanced filters. The equation will be modified to include or exclude Mesh terms as required by different search engines. The search equation is as follows:

((Dengue) OR ("Dengue" [Mesh]) OR ("Breakbone Fever")) AND ((Diagnosis) OR ("Diagnosis" [Mesh]) OR ("Diagnoses and Examinations")) AND (("Signs and Symptoms") OR ("Symptom Assessment"[Mesh]))

Initially, 1677 documents were obtained from all the online databases consulted, covering 1855 to 2024. It was decided to use documents from the year 2000 to 2024 to have a broad and updated period. The selection criterion for selecting documents was to include all those of type Article and exclude all "Literature reviews". This was done through Rayyan (A collaborative web application developed by Qatar Computing Research Institute to streamline literature reviews). Finally, 1224 documents were obtained in this first phase, given that the article's central theme is dengue. Articles containing the word dengue in the title or abstract were selected, and a total of 938 articles were obtained, characterized by their title and, later, their abstract modeled using an LDA model.

Article preparation

For the analysis of frequencies in titles and summaries presented in sections 3.1.1 and 3.1.2, steps 1 to 7 were used for their cleaning (Figure 2). In the same way, the summaries for the construction of the LDA model of section 6 were cleaned.

Figure 2. Stages of the preparation process

Selection of number of topics

In selecting the appropriate number of topics, several measurements, including the calculation of perplexity, were carried out, covering a range from 2 to 20 topics. Subsequently, a graphical technique known as the elbow graph was used to identify the point at which a significant trend change occurred between the measure and the number of topics. This approach posed a significant challenge, as it involved deciding the optimal number of topics. A balance was sought between including many topics, making it difficult to identify critical issues in the analysis, and choosing too few topics, resulting in an excessive mix of topics. In addition, use is made of the implemented metrics in Nikita (2020) corresponding to Arun2010 (Arun et al., 2010), CaoJuan2009 (Cao et al., 2009), Deveaud2014 (Deveaud et al., 2014) y Griffiths2004 (Griffiths and Steyvers, 2004). In addition to the quantitative measures, a biplot was generated for each potential number of topics, a visual tool that allowed us to examine the separation and distribution of the topics in relation to the data in the article abstracts. This visualization was essential to assess the consistency and interpretability of the topics as a function of the number selected.

Resulted

Characterization of articles and magazines

Figure 3 shows the production of articles between the years 2000 and 2024 (January). It can be seen that at the beginning of the period, the production is low, with only two articles, but increases progressively until 2013, where there is a considerable increase that peaks in 2016 (with 81 articles) and a second peak in 2020 (with 92 articles).

Figure 3. Number of items per year

Figure 4 shows the top 15 journals with the highest percentage of articles. It is observed that the journal International Journal of Infectious Diseases has, for the selected articles, the highest SCImago impact indicator (SJR), which suggests it has more significant influence and importance compared to other journals in its area (Medicine) that are in the Scopus base. Another journal that stands out is the Journal of Virology, which has an SJR impact of 1,795, the highest H index (315), and third place in the total number of citations in the last three years. This suggests that these journals have published many high-quality, widely cited articles, contributing to their outstanding reputation.

Figure 4. Featured Magazines

Analysis of word frequency in titles

When performing a frequency analysis of the words present in the titles, it was found that the word dengue had a frequency of 719 times, an expected situation because the presence of the word in the title was an inclusion criterion for the final articles. Based on the words with the highest frequency (Figure 5), it can be mentioned that the selected articles seem to explore aspects such as the epidemiology of dengue and other diseases like Zika or chikungunya, which suggests a consideration of the possible interactions of mosquito-borne diseases, additionally, their presence in different regions such as India, Brazil or endemic, as well as their impact on children. Finding words such as diagnosis, fever, hospital, care, detection, risk, and laboratory suggests that we may be looking at articles covering research related to medical care in hospital settings and others dedicated to the detection, diagnosis, and evaluation of the disease through laboratories.

Figure 5. Frequency of words in titles

Figure 6 shows a bigram for the words included in the titles, showing that there are groups of related words but not connected among all of them; this could be interpreted as the presence of a diversity of topics within the context we are dealing with. There is a notable co-occurrence among the world’s “study”, “cross”, “sectional”, “cohort”, “observational”, and “retrospective” connected to the word study. This pattern points to the inclusion of diverse methodological approaches in the reviewed articles, as evidenced by the different study types mentioned, such as cross-sectional, cohort, observational, and retrospective studies.

Figure 6. Bigram of words in titles

Another segment shows the relationship between the word’s “care”, “hospital”, “intensive”, and “tertiary”, connected by the word “care”, suggesting that they may include articles about medical care and attention. The next segment shows the words “undifferentiated and “acute”, which may refer to an undifferentiated acute syndrome or disease; also, co-occurrences are observed between the word’s “risk” and “factors”, according to Ministerio de Salud y Protección Social – Federación Médica Colombiana (2013) Dengue is an acute viral disease that has various clinical forms, from asymptomatic undifferentiated pictures to severe forms leading to shock and vital organ failure. Finally, the co-occurrence of the word’s “dengue”, “area”, “infection”, “endemic”, “severity”, “fever”, and “hemorrhagic” suggests that the titles of the articles have a thematic focus around dengue, a situation to be expected due to the search equation and inclusion criteria of the selected articles. These articles cover geographical aspects (due to the word endemic), dengue itself, the severity of the disease, symptoms such as fever, and more severe forms such as dengue hemorrhagic fever.

Word frequency analysis in abstracts

Figure 7 shows the frequency of occurrence of words in the abstracts, again highlighting the words “dengue”, “infection”, “study”, “fever”, “diagnostic”, among others, if we compare it with the distribution of the words in the title presented in Figure 5, we find a similar composition. One interpretation of this set of words is that the abstracts of the articles show a tendency to address research on the subject of mosquito-borne diseases, especially dengue, taking into account topics such as diagnosis, laboratory techniques, risk factors, and the presence of the disease in children.

Figure 7. Word frequency in abstracts

Figure 9. Criteria for topic selection through perplexity

Figure 10. Criteria for topic selection using other metrics

Figure 11. Biplot representation of topics

The LDA model is fitted considering different numbers of topics. A biplot is generated for each topic configuration, and it is visually verified that the formed topics are mutually exclusive. This exclusivity is especially evident when comparing the cases of 3 and 4 topics. After reviewing the representations graphically, the decision is made to select the optimal number of topics, 4. In Figure 11, it is found that the topics conformed with $k=4$ are mutually exclusive. In Figure 11, the topics are represented by circles in a two-dimensional plane; their size reflects the importance of the topic in the set of articles (Abstracts); in this case, there is no noticeable difference between the topics.

Finally, the proposed LDA model allocated a percentage of 22.42, 23.80, 27.95, and 25.50 articles for each topic. Figure 12 shows the top 30 words that best present each topic, with which we will proceed to name them in the following sections.

Figure 12. Distribution of words by topic

Topic 1: Diagnosis and clinical presentation

The keywords case, dengue, diagnostic, clinical, fever, symptom, disease, and test suggest that this topic primarily focuses on the diagnosis and clinical presentation, with a greater emphasis on dengue. This idea is reinforced by words such as laboratory, blood, positive, negative, study indicating a connection with laboratory tests and results. Furthermore, using terms such as child, acute and year implies that the subject may pertain to the variation in Dengue presentation across different age groups, including children, acute

syndromes, and various time frames. To explore this topic, a review of the five most relevant articles was conducted in order of significance: [Marks et al. (2016), Kalra et al. (2016), Laoprasopwattana et al. (2020), Herbinger et al. (2011) y da Silva Ferreira et al. (2020)]. The five main articles discuss disease studies, such as Typhoid Fever, Dengue, and Chikungunya. They employ research methods such as retrospective or prospective studies, data analysis, and pilot studies. Each article identifies and differentiates diseases through clinical and laboratory diagnostic methods.

Topic 2: Research and Control Interventions

Keywords such as dengue, study, health, disease, data, result, incidence, transmission, knowledge, model suggest that this topic focuses on Dengue research. In contrast, words such as control, area, risk, vector, surveillance, mosquito, population, community, and intervention indicate a connection with disease control strategies, geographical risk areas, vectors (such as the *Aedes aegypti* mosquito), and surveillance systems. A review of the five most representative articles on the topic is performed in order of representativeness: Sanchez et al. (2005), Nazareth et al. (2014), Jones et al. (2014), Schultes et al. (2021), Nivedita (2016). The five main articles have in common that they deal with studies to understand, evaluate, or improve dengue control strategies in different regions such as Cuba, Madeira, and Belo Horizonte (Brazil). Each article presents specific interventions designed to control the spread of the dengue virus, either through policy changes Sanchez et al. (2005), evaluation of community perceptions Nazareth et al. (2014); Nivedita (2016), implementation of new tools such as insecticidal screens Jones et al. (2014), spatial pattern analysis or health education programs Schultes et al. (2021).

Topic 3: Severe Dengue and Clinical Manifestations (Signs and Symptoms)

Keywords such as dengue, patient, fever, severe, severity, dhf (dengue hemorrhagic fever), haemorrhagic, syndorme, day, study, death, manifestation, care, shock, platelet, thrombocytopenia suggest that this topic focuses on aspects related to severe cases of dengue, the clinical manifestation of the disease and possible complications. The presence of terms such as hospital, age, group suggests a connection with the presence of different age groups, genders, and the hospital environment. A review of the five most representative articles on the topic was carried out in order of representativeness: Parkash et al. (2010), Iqtadar et al. (2017), Khetpal et al. (2021), Thomas et al. (2010), Khurram et al. (2016). The top five articles focus on research dealing with clinical manifestations of dengue, such as plasma leakage [29], progression of dengue to severe cases Khetpal et al. (2021), Thomas et al. (2010), and hepatic manifestations, which can be seen in Parkash et al. (2010), and Iqtadar et al. (2017).

Topic 4: Virus Detection (Dengue, Zika or Chikungunya)

Keywords such as infection, denv (dengue virus), virus, zika, sample, chikungunya suggest that this topic focuses on studies on diseases transmitted by mosquitoes that could be targeted with diagnostic tests due to the presence of words like ns, igm, igg, pcr, elisa, protein, detection, cell, detection, human, positive, serum in the same way connection with the characterization of the virus by the presence of words like serotype, rna. Now, including words like response, time, and vaccine could indicate the inclusion of research on vaccination strategies. Finally, the word co could indicate the presence of research that mentions co-infection. The five most representative articles on the topic were reviewed in the order of representativeness; they are Chatel-Chaix et al. (2015), Morizono and Chen (2014), Xie et al. (2015), Chiang et al. (2015), Pattabhi et al. (2016).

The five main articles deal with Dengue viruses, but others mention Zika and Chikungunya. The articles are focused on understanding and addressing viral infections, whether by mapping critical determinants for replication Chatel-Chaix et al. (2015), exploring molecules related to viral infection Morizono and Chen (2014), Xie et al. (2015), Pattabhi et al. (2016), or designing RNA agonists with enhanced inflammatory antiviral properties against influenza, dengue, and chikungunya viruses Chiang et al. (2015).

Conclusions

During this research, an analysis of the articles related to dengue has been carried out, focusing on the characterization and modeling of their summaries. Developing a search equation with MeSH terms allowed access to various health and medicine research databases, including sources such as ScienceDirect, which covers a wide scientific range. From this review, a classification of articles has been identified in four main categories: Diagnosis and clinical presentation, Research and control interventions, Severe dengue and clinical manifestations, and Detection of the virus (Dengue, Zika, or Chikungunya).

This thematic diversity highlights the breadth of research approaches related to dengue, providing a solid foundation for future researchers to explore various lines of study. As a recommendation for subsequent research, it is suggested that the full content of the articles be considered, since summaries may omit crucial details for modeling. Furthermore, implementing alternative modeling strategies, such as Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) or Probabilistic Latent Semantic Analysis (pLSA), could enrich the analysis and provide a complete view of the topics addressed. Likewise, the results underline the importance of using unsupervised learning tools, such as the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) model, in literature reviews. This approach has proven instrumental in addressing the vast collection of documents related to a specific topic, streamlining the review process and allowing researchers to focus on the documents most relevant to their studies. The specific case of this

research began with 938 articles, which were efficiently segmented into groups of 211, 224, 263, and 240, respectively. This methodology facilitates a more detailed review of each group, depending on the line of research intended to be followed.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Author contribution statement

All the authors declare that the final version of this paper was read and approved. Authors and CRediT Roles: J.P.Y.: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Software, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization. A. F. P. M.: Investigation, Software, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization. D. F. M.: Supervision, Project administration. J. R. T. C: Supervision, Project administration. Writing – review & editing.

The total contribution percentage for this paper was as follows: J.P.Y. 40 %, A.F.P.M: 30 %, D.F.M: 15 % and J. R. T.C: 15 %.

Data availability statement

Information supporting the results of this study will be made available by the corresponding author J.P.Y. upon reasonable request.

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